

Deliverable D2.4

General toolbox for gene editing in plants and microalgae

May 31st, 2025

Document Control Sheet

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Task Leader (Name and Short Org. Name)	Fabien Nogu; INRAE
Main Author (Name and Short Org. Name)	Katrijn Van Laere; EV-ILVO
Other Authors (Name and Short Org. Name)	Elke Vereecke (EV-ILVO); Tom Ruttink (EV-ILVO)
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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
CRISPR/Cas	Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
gRNA	Guide RNA
NGT	New Genomic Technique
PCR	Polymerase Chain Reaction
R&I	Research and Innovation
RNP	Ribonucleoprotein
NHEJ	Non-homologous end joining
HDR	Homology-Directed repair
VIB	Flemish Institute for Biotechnology
MTA	Material Transfer Agreement

Table of contents

1. About the GeneBEcon Project	6
2. Executive Summary	7
3. Introduction	8
4. An open access database with GeneBEcon plasmids	9
5. GeneBEwise – Gene editing workflow and instructions for scientists.....	11
6. Exploitation of GeneBEwise.....	13
7. Conclusion.....	13
RRI Questionnaire	14
Annexes	16

1. About the GeneBEcon Project

GeneBEcon - capturing the potential of Gene editing for a sustainable BioEconomy

GeneBEcon is a Horizon Europe-funded project which examines the innovative potential of gene editing to enable a sustainable bioeconomy in Europe. Through the application of this technology in potato and microalgae, GeneBEcon intends to promote energy-efficient, low-input, and zero-pollution agricultural production and clean industrial processing.

New Genomic Techniques (NGTs) represent a powerful toolbox (complementary to traditional breeding techniques) addressing current pressing challenges, including pollution and climate change. However, these techniques have not yet reached their full potential in Europe. GeneBEcon will advance research and innovation, acting on two fronts: through new gene editing developments at the technological level, as well as considering social, economic, and regulatory dimensions.

Among NGTs, gene editing holds the greatest potential for contributing to the ambitious objectives of the European Green Deal, the 2030 Climate Target Plan, and the Circular Economy Action Plan. Nonetheless, risks and benefits must be assessed to ensure that gene editing innovations like any other type of innovation are developed in a responsible, inclusive, and transparent way. GeneBEcon aims to address these concerns and propel Europe towards a cleaner, more sustainable and zero-pollution agricultural and industrial production.

GeneBEcon will construct a toolbox for gene editing using potato and microalgae as case studies and it will assess regulatory options, analyze the economic impact and consider societal perceptions. The gene-edited potato will enable reduced use of pesticides potato cultivation and it will produce a higher quality starch allowing a more environmentally friendly potato starch processing saving up to 75,000 tonnes of chemicals and 7.5 GWh of energy in the EU every year. Likewise, gene-edited microalgae will allow resource-efficient and clean production of industrially relevant compounds and the repurposing of microalgae residual biomass as animal feed will considerably reduce waste production and CO₂ emissions. GeneBEcon has a budget of 5.5 million Euros and a duration of three years as of September 1 2022. GeneBEcon is executed by a multidisciplinary consortium with leading scientists from 11 European countries and in interdisciplinary collaboration with stakeholders.

Partners:

Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences,
Sweden – Project Coordinator
XPRO Consulting Limited, Cyprus
SolEdits AB, Sweden
Latvijas Universitate, Latvia
FN3PT/inov3PT, France
INRAE, France
Euroseeds, Belgium
Danish Technological Institute, Denmark
Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra,
Slovakia

EV-ILVO, Belgium
Plants for the Future ETP, Belgium
Wageningen University, the Netherlands
BVL, Germany
Universität Bayreuth, Germany
Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação, Portugal
HZPC Research BV, the Netherlands
INVE Belgie, Belgium
Associated Partner:
WBF-Agroscope, Switzerland

For more information, please contact:

Dennis ERIKSSON, Project Coordinator

Department of Plant Breeding, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Sweden

E-mail: dennis.eriksson@slu.se

Website: <https://www.slu.se/en/ew-cv/dennis-eriksson/>

2. Executive Summary

To evaluate the possibilities of New Genomic Techniques (NGTs) to enhance plant research and breeding efficiency in potatoes, and to optimize strain selection in microalgae, a comprehensive toolbox with up-to-date tools and protocols for gene editing is essential. Therefore, the GeneBEcon partners, the Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (EV-ILVO), the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU), and the Institut national de recherche pour l'agriculture, l'alimentation et l'environnement (INRAE), gathered their existing methods and co-developed new gene editing tools and protocols and shared these in a publicly accessible online gene editing toolbox, GeneBEwise. In GeneBEwise, the tools and protocols are organized as a comprehensive, “decision tree”-based workflow that covers the entire gene editing process – from target selection, via design and delivery of CRISPR/Cas components, to molecular screening methods for gene-edited materials.

The GeneBEwise toolbox is accessible on <https://genebewise.genebecon.eu/>. It provides a user-friendly “decision tree”-based interface that guides users (in particular, scientists and breeders) to protocols relevant to their specific (multiplex) gene editing experiment. In addition, it offers general information about the various protocols and techniques involved in the gene editing process, ensuring that users can make informed decisions about which strategy (for example, CRISPR strategy, transformation strategy, etc.) to use. GeneBEwise consists of four different panels. The first panel includes all the tools needed to identify and characterize the target gene sequence(s). The second panel outlines strategies to design gRNAs for different gene editing applications. Where the first two panels focus mainly on bioinformatics methods, the third and fourth panel cover experimental protocols. The third panel includes protocols for plasmid cloning, RNP assembly, transformation and regeneration, while the fourth panel focuses on molecular screening for mutants/mutant alleles in the laboratory.

The GeneBEwise workflow, protocols, and materials (e.g. plasmids) aim to improve the effectiveness and accuracy of commonly used CRISPR/Cas tools for non-homologous end joining (NHEJ), as well as more advanced techniques, such as base editing, prime editing, and homology-directed repair (HDR). They can be freely used after registration on the GeneBEwise website. All plasmids used within GeneBEcon and GeneBEwise are also publicly available at <https://vectorvault.vib.be/genebecon>. To ensure global compatibility, sustainable use of the plasmids, they are based on international standard cloning vector systems. The plasmids can be ordered from the Vectorvault repository and used after signing an MTA stating that the plasmids are only used for non-commercial academic research purposes. In addition, GeneBEwise includes plasmid-free methods such as ribonucleoprotein (RNP) complexes and transient transfection systems, which reduce the probability of integration of exogenous DNA into the genome of gene-edited plants or microalgae.

The GeneBEwise toolbox will have broad applicability in potato and microalgae and its use can be extended to other organisms and species. At this point, many of the GeneBEwise tools are also validated in *Cichorium* and *Physcomitrium*. After the GeneBEcon project has ended, project partners will engage to update the GeneBEwise toolbox and validate tools in more crops, ensuring its broad applicability in the future.

The main target group of GeneBEwise includes scientists and breeders interested in developing or applying gene editing techniques in potato, microalgae, and other plant species. Users will come from universities, research institutes, academic laboratories and R&D companies focusing on agri-biotech and plant breeding, who will use the toolbox both for fundamental and applied research. Also stakeholders and decision makers will be using the GeneBEwise toolbox as they will need understanding of gene editing to take decisions on NGT products.

3. Introduction

Work package 2 (WP2) of GeneBEcon, “Advancing NGTs in biobased R&I”, focuses on advancing and using gene editing tools to create innovative potato and microalgae varieties with enhanced value for biobased applications. For potato, gene editing is applied to improve resistance against potato virus Y (PVY), which is one of the most destructive viruses in potato crops, and to optimize starch quality for industrial applications, eliminating the need for chemical processing of starch before use. For microalgae, the focus is on strain optimization and enhancing the production of high-value compounds like carotenoids, which can be used in pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries.

To modify such complex traits through gene editing, it is crucial to have access to up-to-date and validated tools and protocols for plasmid cloning, transformation and regeneration, and molecular screening to identify candidate mutant events. In addition, for many crops including potato, extra challenges are posed due to their complex genomes (e.g. tetraploidy in potato). Similarly, genome editing in microalgae is limited by several factors, including the lack of comprehensive genome resources and databases, and the absence of standardized transformation protocols for the delivery of the CRISPR editing components, mainly due to the rigid cell wall in most microalgae species. Besides the use of non-homologous end-joining (NHEJ) to knockout genes, also more advanced CRISPR/Cas systems, such as base editing, prime editing, and homology-directed repair (HDR), can be used to induce very precise mutations. However, these tools are still inefficient and poorly adapted for potato and microalgae genome editing.

In literature, efficient protocols are not always easy to find and, in many cases, they are only very briefly described and poorly detailed. Scientists and breeders that want to perform gene editing experiments have a need for user-friendly and ready-to-use protocols and workflows as a basis to start further optimization in their specific crop. In addition, many scientists use plasmids for specific applications. However, these plasmids could also be applicable for other crops and applications. A central database containing plasmids with detailed description of their use and features is thus of added value.

To accommodate to these needs and challenges, within GeneBEcon, a comprehensive up-to-date gene editing toolbox containing user-friendly protocols and tools and a plasmid database are constructed. Among GeneBEcon partners several protocols for gene editing were already available prior to the start of the project, and new protocols were co-developed during the project. The GeneBEcon WP2 partners (EV-ILVO, SLU, and INRAE) have shared their already existing and newly developed tools, protocols and plasmids and made all these publicly available. It comprises state-of-the-art CRISPR/Cas9 based constructs, versatile cloning strategies, optimized DNA delivery and regeneration systems, and bioinformatics pipelines for the integrated design of gRNAs taking the efficiency and specificity (knowledge about gene family members) into account. To structure all these resources, a “decision tree”-based approach was chosen, decorated with all protocols. This approach offers two key advantages: (1) it provides extra context and information to help researchers make informed decisions about which technique to use and, (2) it guides them to the specific protocols relevant to their gene editing experiment (based on the choices that they have made). As a result, the toolbox allows for high-precision gene editing while minimizing unwanted alterations to the original genomes.

The main target customers of the toolbox and plasmid database are researchers from universities, research institutes, academic laboratories, plant breeders, and private R&D agro-biotech companies focusing on trait discovery, strain optimization, and breeding. Customers will use the toolbox for research and breeding purposes, both fundamental and applied research, and proof of concept studies. In addition, also governmental and non-governmental organizations and policy makers can be target groups of the toolbox as it can equip stakeholders, risk assessors and decision makers with the needed understanding to take decisions on NGT-derived products.

4. An open access database with GeneBEcon plasmids

The collection of 111 plasmids, containing plasmids developed at INRAE and EV-ILVO is attached (annex#1). These plasmids, along with their annotated vector sequences and detailed information, are publicly accessible via <https://vectorvault.vib.be/genebecon>. The platform to make the plasmids publicly available was chosen based on several criteria. The research data repository should: (1) provide clear information for each plasmid, (2) offer open access to its data, (3) define clear terms of use and licenses, and (4) use a persistent identifier system in accordance with the FAIR principles of data sharing. Additionally, as the GeneBEcon project is a European Union-funded project, data repositories established in Europe were prioritized. For this, we chose the VectorVault database, an existing platform from VIB-UGent, Center for Plant Systems Biology (Gent, Belgium), that fulfills all the selection criteria. A dedicated page has been created within the VectorVault database for the GeneBEcon plasmids, providing visibility to the GeneBEcon project outcome (Figure 1). Plasmids can be ordered at cost price (75€/plasmid) through the webpage (Figure 2), following signing of an MTA stating that plasmids can only be used for research purposes (annex#2). All the GeneBEcon plasmids were sent as a stab culture to VIB and are maintained by technical staff of VIB. Bilateral MTAs were signed between the individual GeneBEcon partner (INRAE and EV-ILVO) and VIB stipulating that VIB will add the plasmids to the repository, maintain the plasmids and ship them to researchers that purchase the plasmids. The VIB system allows monitoring of the number of webpage visitors and of plasmid orders, hence enabling to estimate GeneBEcon outcome impact.

The screenshot shows the VectorVault website interface. At the top left is the VIB-UGent Center for Plant Systems Biology logo. The navigation menu includes HOME, COLLECTION (highlighted), ORDERING INFORMATION, PLASMID INFORMATION, PUBLICATIONS, FAQ, and CONTACT. A shopping cart icon is visible on the right. Below the navigation is a dark blue banner with the text "Building Blocks" and "Specific Plasmid Sets". The breadcrumb trail reads: VIB > VIB-UGent Center for Plant Systems Biology > Vector Vault > Collection > Specific Plasmid Sets > GeneBEcon. The main heading is "GeneBEcon". Below it is a sub-heading "GeneBEcon - Capturing the potential of Gene editing for a sustainable BioEconomy". The text describes the project as a Horizon Europe-funded project from September 2022 to August 2025, aimed at enabling a sustainable bioeconomy in Europe through gene editing in potato and microalgae. It mentions a toolbox for gene editing and the integration of plasmids into the Vector Vault repository. The text also states the aim of gene editing in potato (increased resistance to Potato Virus Y and enhanced starch quality) and in green microalgae (increased production of high-value compounds like lutein). It notes that the project was executed by a multidisciplinary consortium of 18 partners from 11 European countries. At the bottom of the text area, there is the GeneBEcon logo, the URL <https://genebecon.eu>, and the Cordis project ID <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101081015>. Below this are three teal buttons: "Entry Vectors", "Destination Vectors", and "Expression Vectors". At the very bottom, there is a link to "Download the entire archive here".

Figure 1: Printscreen of the webpage of VectorVault where GeneBEcon plasmids are publicly available.

pDe-SaCas9-Alt

Vector ID: 24_12

Application CRISPR	Species Dicots
Backbone Binary	Bacterial selection Spectinomycin
Vector type GW Destination	Plant selectable marker Kanamycin
Bacterial strain ccdB	Codon optimization Dicotyledon codon optimized
Created 3/12/2024	Remarks KO of eIF4E allele 1 in Altesse
Publications GeneBEcon	

↓ DOWNLOAD .GB FILE

Order Vector

Price **75,00 EUR**
(VAT excl.)

Quantity

LOG IN

Minimum purchase order is 150,00€. Free shipping on all products.

Figure 2: Example of representation of a plasmid on the VectorVault webpage. Plasmids can be ordered. The GenBank (.gb) file with plasmid sequence and structural annotation can be downloaded.

All vectors are based on international standard cloning vector systems (e.g. Golden Gate Cloning) to ensure global compatibility, sustainable access, and transparent documentation. This will allow future users to easily and modularly assemble the different elements of CRISPR modules. Most plasmids are constructed using widely available vector backbone materials (including Addgene or Gateway) combined with in-house developed functional sequence elements. These in-house modifications included changing the promoter driving CRISPR/Cas protein expression *in planta*, adding nuclear localization sequences (NLS) for enhanced nuclear localization of the CRISPR enzyme and increase editing efficiency, incorporating species-specific and/or tissue-specific promoters (potato), and adding CRISPR enzyme variants for base editing, prime editing and CRISPR-NHEJ. Novel vector constructs were assembled for specific applications in potato and microalgae but are also applicable to other plant species (currently tested in *Cichorium* and *Physcomitrium*), thereby broadening the toolbox's range of use.

All plasmid sequences are provided in the universal GenBank .gb format. This format is a text-based document with sequence and annotation information that can be viewed using a simple text editor (e.g., Notepad, Text Edit) or specialized sequence analysis software (e.g., SnapGene, Geneious, CLC-bio Genomics Workbench).

5. GeneBEwise – Gene editing workflow and instructions for scientists

The collaborative effort of EV-ILVO, INRAE and SLU led to the co-development of efficient gene editing tools for potato and microalgae, organized into a comprehensive toolbox. The toolbox is named “GeneBEwise – gene editing workflow and instructions for scientists” and is publicly online available at: <https://genebewise.genebecon.eu/>.

To structure all available knowledge and protocols, a guided workflow was constructed and divided into four panels (Figure 3). The idea is that, by answering a series of questions - each accompanied with the necessary context - the user gains a better understanding of the workflow and can generate a checklist of what is needed to proceed to the next step or panel (Figure 4). If the user cannot answer a particular question, an information page appears explaining how to obtain the required data. The GeneBEwise website is designed so that, based on the user's responses, new pages open that are tailored to their specific situation. In this “decision tree”-based approach, only the information and protocols relevant to the user's experiment are shown, preventing them from getting lost in the wide range of available techniques. However, if the user prefers to explore the full set of options, they can navigate freely through the different sections using the content menu on the left hand side of the website.

Figure 3: Printscreen of the GeneBEwise homepage, showing the 4 panels.

Panel 1 provides a step-by-step approach to identify candidate target genes. It covers bioinformatics software that help gathering detailed information about the target gene, such as its sequence, annotation, genomic position and gene family memberships, as well as identifying sequences with sequence similarity to the target gene. The output of panel 1 serves as input for panel 2.

Panel 2 selects a CRISPR strategy (NHEJ, base editing, prime editing, or HDR) and a list of software is provided to design gRNAs tailored to user's experimental needs (either highly specific to target a single gene, or broader to target multiple genes). Depending on the chosen CRISPR strategy, panel 2 also offers

guidance on CRISPR strategy-related constructs, such as which base editor or donor repair template to use.

Panel 3 focusses on CRISPR/Cas plasmid cloning, delivery of DNA (plasmids, RNPs) into the cell (transfection) or plant tissue (transformation), and regeneration systems for potato and microalgae. It includes detailed protocols that guide users through all practical steps of the workflow, from tissue preparation to transfection, regeneration, and culture. The protocols for potato protoplast and microalgae transfection are designed to be user-friendly and ready-to-use, with precise pipetting schemes and instructions, making them far more elaborate than what is usually found in the Materials and Methods section of published scientific literature. Especially for regeneration, which is often a bottleneck in plant gene editing workflows, these detailed protocols provide practical tips and tricks to enhance regeneration efficiency. Some protocols (for example, potato transfection and regeneration) were actively exchanged between laboratories for validation and to ensure exchangeability of protocols in practice. For example, INRAE evaluated media described in protocols from SLU.

Panel 4 focuses on tools and methods for screening CRISPR-induced mutations. It includes both PCR-based and sequencing-based methods, as well as bioinformatics software for data analysis. These methods can be used both to screen for the intended CRISPR-induced mutations, but also to identify the presence of unintended (off-target) mutations.

In the GeneBEwise toolbox protocols are included for gene editing in potato and microalgae (*Chlorella*, *Nannochloropsis*). However, some of these tools and protocols have already been validated in other crops in the labs of EV-ILVO, INRAE or SLU, e.g. in *Cichorium* and *Physcomitrium*.

PANEL 2

Home > Panel 2 > Mutation type

MUTATION TYPE

Do you aim for a pre-defined mutation of a non-defined mutation at a specific location on the target gene?

Pre-defined mutation Non-defined mutation

CONTEXT

In CRISPR experiments, mutations can be broadly categorized as pre-defined or non-defined.

Pre-defined mutations are specific alterations in the DNA sequence that are precisely defined on beforehand, such as insertion of a particular sequence, specific substitution of nucleotides, or the creation of a targeted deletion of a specific size. The exact nature of the change, down to the affected nucleotides, is pre-determined during the design phase of the CRISPR experiment.

Non-defined mutations are alterations in the DNA sequence that are defined in genomic location but not in terms of the exact nucleotide changes introduced. So whether a deletion, insertion, or substitution is introduced, and the specific nucleotides involved, is not predetermined. Non-defined mutations arise due to the inherent variability in how the DNA repair mechanisms, such as non-homologous end joining (NHEJ), repair the double-strand

Figure 4: Example of the GeneBEwise pages, showing how the pages are built. A specific question is asked to the users, accompanied by some context to understand the question properly. Based on the answer that the user gives, a new page will open to proceed to the next step in the gene editing workflow.

An ethical clause has been included on the home page of GeneBEwise: “Anyone utilizing the GeneBEwise toolbox is expected to adhere to the highest standards of ethical responsibility. This includes compliance with relevant regulations, consideration of potential societal and environmental impacts, and a commitment to transparency and inclusivity in the application of gene editing technologies. The toolbox is more than a resource — it is a tool for advancing innovation in a way that respects both human and ecological well-being, ensuring that its use contributes positively to the global bioeconomy. The toolbox is designed to be used in compliance with ethical standards and regulatory frameworks, ensuring gene editing applications benefit society while minimizing potential risks”. In addition, users will need to register before they can

access the GeneBEwise website. Registration is free but will enable the website host to have indications on how widely the GeneBEwise website is consulted and used.

6. Exploitation of GeneBEwise

The GeneBEwise toolbox has been made open access to all the target customers. During the GeneBEcon project, the webpage is hosted on the GeneBEcon website. However, after the GeneBEcon project ends, one of the consortium partners, most likely EV-ILVO, will take over the webpage and host it on the institutes website, while maintaining visibility and acknowledgement of the GeneBEcon project. The necessary steps are undertaken during the development of the GeneBEwise website to guarantee that transferring the website to another host can be easily done. The toolbox will be updated in the future when new protocols are developed or when new relevant protocols are found in literature. In addition, an open access article will be published describing the toolbox and its added value and use

The plasmids are added to the open access Vectorvault repository hosted by VIB which is a research institute in Belgium that closely collaborates with EV-ILVO, one of the GeneBEcon consortium partners. Researchers or other customers that purchase a plasmid from this repository will have to sign an MTA mainly stating that plasmids can only be used for research activities and not for commercial applications. Plasmids developed after the GeneBEcon project will not be added to the Vectorvault repository, unless the specific partner agrees otherwise with VIB. In that case an agreement between the specific partner and VIB will be made.

The toolbox focused on protocols validated in potato and microalgae. However, the GeneBEwise protocols can be used as a basis for genome editing in other crops. If users have questions, they can be addressed to researchers within the GeneBEcon consortium.

7. Conclusion

The GeneBEwise toolbox and plasmid database are developed for efficient gene editing in potato and strain optimization in microalgae. They comprise all necessary methods and materials for performing CRISPR/Cas gene editing: more specifically to carry out the (in)activation of a gene (via NHEJ) or its precise modification via base editing, prime editing, or homology-directed repair (HDR). Bioinformatics methods are included to streamline gRNA design, taking gRNA efficiency and specificity into account as well as prior knowledge of gene family members, *within*-genome sequence similarity to gRNA binding off-targets, and *within*-cultivar allelic diversity of gRNA target sequences. A description of relevant bioinformatics software is also included to design targeted re-sequencing panels to evaluate induced mutations, fully compatible with commonly used sequencing platforms and technologies. All methods are designed to be scalable for multiplex CRISPR/Cas applications.

Our GeneBEwise toolbox has some unique features. First, it contains tools and protocols enabling a species-specific design and optimization of gene editing experiments. Second, all protocols, tools and materials (e.g. plasmids) are gathered all in one place, i.e. the GeneBEwise website. The 111 plasmids are constructed based on widely used vector backbones and using overall compatible cloning strategies. The protocols are ready-to-use and user friendly. Third, GeneBEwise is constructed based on a decision tree, which is ideal to follow a logic workflow going over all steps needed to perform a successful gene editing experiment.

By making the toolbox publicly accessible via a website, it will reach the entire R&I and breeders community, hence enabling a broad applicability in potato and microalgae and beyond, as the proposed workflow and protocols are transferable or can be used as a starting point to optimize gene editing tools in other crops. Furthermore, our open access toolbox can be presented to competent national and EU authorities as a blueprint for molecular analytical tools to analyze NGT products.

RRI Questionnaire

Question	Answer
1. How has the RRI concept been considered in the completed work?	During WP2 joined meetings with EV-ILVO, INRAE and SLU, partners discussed how the Toolbox could be organized to promote the responsible use of the plasmids and protocols. WP2 partners took known concerns of stakeholders into account in their discussions, e.g. this led to the decisions to: include DNA-free methods in the Toolbox, make the Toolbox open access, but with registration, add approaches to design sequence-specific gRNAs and avoid off-target editing, etc.
2. Have stakeholders been consulted during the work?	Yes
a. How?	During the consortium meetings, where also SAB members were present, the GeneBEwise toolbox was presented. Stakeholders could provide feedback at these moments.
b. What inputs have been obtained during the interaction with the stakeholders?	Main concerns were raised on the ethical use of the plasmids and toolbox.
c. Have these inputs changed the considerations of the work?	Based on the stakeholders concerns, we implemented a registration module for users of the toolbox and added an ethical statement on the home page of the toolbox. Concerning the plasmid database, researchers that want to order a plasmid, will be asked to sign an MTA in which it is stated that the plasmids can only be used for research purposes.
3. In involving stakeholders, did you have to explain the science behind the work? Please explain how you did this.	Yes, we explained the science and rationale through a detailed Powerpoint presentation during the meeting where SAB members were present.
4. Explain the Ethical procedures you are following in the course of the completed work.	Principles and guidelines that ensure the responsible and moral conduct of scientific research are followed by the different partners. These include but are not limited to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - partners were honest, accurate, and transparent when reporting their findings, - partners protected the privacy and confidentiality of individuals or organizations involved in the WP, - partners ensured that data is collected, stored, and shared in a secure and anonymized manner, - partners disclosed any potential conflicts of interest that could influence the design, conduct, or reporting of their research, - Partners respected intellectual property rights, including patents, copyrights, and trade secrets, while appropriately crediting and citing the work of others. - On the website of the GeneBEwise toolbox a paragraph on ethical use of the toolbox was included. Users have

	to formally agree on this ethical statement before being able to use the toolbox.
5. Have you considered any gender issues in the work?	To reach this deliverable, we shared the protocols and plasmids available in laboratories of several partners, made and created by the people that worked on gene editing projects in our institutes. The institutes involved in WP2 recruited people to do research based on their qualifications and capabilities, and this was also the case to 'recruit' the people that work on WP2. There are no gender issues seen in the development of the Toolbox, the Toolbox can and will be used by all scientists/breeders qualified/educated to use these tools.
a. Which ones?	N/A
b. How did they affect the work and/ or results?	N/A
6. What kind of open science actions have you included in the work and results?	The Toolbox and plasmids are made publicly available and findable.
7. In this Deliverable/ Milestone, what kind of governance/ regulation issues do you foresee?	The upcoming European Commission legal proposal on plants developed by directed mutagenesis and cis-genesis will likely affect positively the use of the Toolbox by creating a stronger demand for innovation and development towards commercialization in the European Union.
a. What kind of change to a product-based regulatory system could enable its wider acceptance by taking into account	
i. the development stage of the product,	
ii. its benefits and risks, and	
iii. its degree of certainty about its future properties.	

Annexes

Annex 1: list of plasmids added to the VectorVault database

Vector Name	Applications	Species	Backbone	Vector type	Bacterial selection	Plant selection	Bacterial strain	Ownership
GB zCas9i-RY S2-S7	CRISPR KO	Dicots	High copy	Golden Gate	Ampicillin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
pUPD2-pcoCas9	CRISPR KO	Dicots	High copy	Golden Gate	Chloramphenicol	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
a1 pRPS5A-zCas9iRY-trbcSE9	CRISPR KO	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
a1 pRPS5A-zCas9i-trbcSE9	CRISPR KO	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
a1 proEggCell-pcoCas9-trbcSE9	CRISPR KO	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
a1 proEggCell-zCas9i-trbcSE9	CRISPR KO	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
o2 pRPS5a-zCas9i - DsRed	CRISPR KO	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Spectinomycin	Fluorescence	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
o2 pEC-pcoCas9 - DsRed	CRISPR KO	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Spectinomycin	Fluorescence	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
o2 pEC-zCas9i - DsRed	CRISPR KO	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Spectinomycin	Fluorescence	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
a2 pZmUbi-pcoCas9-trbcS3a	CRISPR KO	Plants	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
a1 NeoR-pZmUbi-pcoCas9-trbcS3a	CRISPR KO	Plants	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	Kanamycin	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
a1 pZmUbi-zCas9iRY-trbcSE9	CRISPR KO	Plants	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
pAct-Cas9	CRISPR KO	Plants	High copy	Expression	Ampicillin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
pAct-CjCAS9	CRISPR KO	Plants	Binary	Expression	Ampicillin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
pUPD2-nCAS9 PmCDA1	CRISPR Base editing	Dicots	High copy	Golden Gate	Chloramphenicol	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
PpCBE1	CRISPR Base editing	Dicots	Binary	Expression	Spectinomycin	Kanamycin	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
a1 pEggCell-nCas9H840-MMV-RT-tSE9	CRISPR Prime editing	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
a1 pRPS5a-nCas9H840-MMV-RT-tSE9	CRISPR Prime editing	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
o2 pEggCell-nCas9H840-MMV-RT-tSE9-DsRed	CRISPR Prime editing	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Spectinomycin	Fluorescence	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
o2 pRPS5a-nCas9H840-MMV-RT-tSE9-DsRed.gb	CRISPR Prime editing	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Spectinomycin	Fluorescence	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
a1 pM4-znCas9i-MMLVRNase-tSE9	CRISPR Prime editing	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
pACT-PE	CRISPR Prime editing	Plants	High copy	Expression	Ampicillin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
GB proPpU3-1	Promoter (PolIII)	Physcomitrella	High copy	Golden Gate	Chloramphenicol	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles

GB proPpU6-1	Promoter (PolIII)	Physcomitrella	High copy	Golden Gate	Chloramphenicol	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
GB esgRNA scaffold	gRNA scaffold	Plants	High copy	Golden Gate	Chloramphenicol	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
GB proEggCell	Promoter (PolIII)	Dicots	High copy	Golden Gate	Chloramphenicol	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
GB RbcSE9Ter	Terminator	Dicots	High copy	Golden Gate	Chloramphenicol	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
GB pRPS5A	Promoter (PolIII)	Dicots	High copy	Golden Gate	Chloramphenicol	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
GB AtUbi10	Promoter (PolIII)	Dicots	High copy	Golden Gate	Ampicillin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
GB VvUbi2pro	Promoter (PolIII)	Other	High copy	Golden Gate	Ampicillin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
GB proVvU6-1	Promoter (PolIII)	Other	High copy	Golden Gate	Ampicillin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
GB proVvU6-2	Promoter (PolIII)	Other	High copy	Golden Gate	Ampicillin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
GB SpectR	Selectable Marker	Plants	High copy	Golden Gate	Ampicillin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
GB Rbcs3aTer	Terminator	Dicots	High copy	Golden Gate	Chloramphenicol	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
GB GmHSP	Promoter (PolIII)	Dicots	High copy	Golden Gate	Ampicillin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
GB proSIU3-1	Promoter (PolIII)	Other	High copy	Golden Gate	Ampicillin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
GB proSIU6-1	Promoter (PolIII)	Other	High copy	Golden Gate	Ampicillin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
GB pZmUBI	Promoter (PolIII)	Monocots	High copy	Golden Gate	Chloramphenicol	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
GB GmScrM4pro	Promoter (PolIII)	Other	High copy	Golden Gate	Chloramphenicol	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
a2 HygR	Selectable Marker	Plants	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	Hygromycin	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
a2 pCsVMV ::DsRed-Trbcs3a	Fluorescent Reporter	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	Fluorescence	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
a1 pZmUBI-mCherry-tSE9	Selectable Marker	Plants	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	Fluorescence	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
GB MoMLV-RT	CRISPR Prime editing	Dicots	High copy	Golden Gate	Chloramphenicol	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
GB nCas9 H840A no stop	CRISPR Prime editing	Dicots	High copy	Golden Gate	Chloramphenicol	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
GB MoMLV-RTdeltaRNase	CRISPR Prime editing	Dicots	High copy	Golden Gate	Chloramphenicol	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
GB znCAS9i	CRISPR KO	Dicots	High copy	Golden Gate	Spectinomycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
pDe-CAS9-D10A	CRISPR Nickase	Plants	Binary	Expression	Spectinomycin	Basta	ccdB	INRAE-Versailles
pACT-CasRX	CRISPR KO	Plants	High copy	Expression	Ampicillin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
pAct-nCas9-H840A	CRISPR Nickase	Plants	High Copy	Expression	Spectinomycin	Basta	DH10B	INRAE-Versailles
a2 StUBI-GFP-S3a 2	Fluorescent Reporter	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	Fluorescence	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
a1 2x35S-GFP-tS3a	Fluorescent Reporter	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	Fluorescence	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
a2-pZmUbi eGFP	Fluorescent Reporter	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	Fluorescence	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
2x35S::Basta a1	Selectable Marker	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	Basta	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
2x35S::Basta a2	Selectable Marker	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	Basta	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
2x35s::GFP 2x35S::Basta o1	Selectable Marker	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Spectinomycin	Basta	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
2x35s::GFP 2x35S::Basta o2	Selectable Marker	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Spectinomycin	Basta	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel

2x35s::GFP 2x35S::Basta AtRPS5::zCas9i a2	CRISPR KO	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	Basta	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
StUBI::zCas9i a1	CRISPR KO	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
StUBI::zCas9i a2	CRISPR KO	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
StUBI::PPE2 a1	CRISPR Prime editing	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
StUBI::PPE2 a2	CRISPR Prime editing	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
StUBI::GFP StUBI::PPE2 o2	CRISPR Prime editing	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Spectinomycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
StUBI::GFP StUBI::PPE2 T1-T2-T3-T4-T1d a2	CRISPR Prime editing	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
StUBI::GFP StUBI::PPE2 T1-T2-T3-T4-T5 a2	CRISPR Prime editing	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
StUBI::GFP StUBI::PPE2 T1-T2-T3-T4-T1d NPTII o1	CRISPR Prime editing	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Spectinomycin	Kanamycin	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
StUBI::GFP StUBI::PPE2 T1-T2-T3-T4-T5 NPTII o1	CRISPR Prime editing	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Spectinomycin	Kanamycin	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
ZmUBI::PPE2 a1	CRISPR Prime editing	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
ZmUBI::PPE2 a2	CRISPR Prime editing	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
StUBI::GFP StUBI::zCas9i T1-T2-T3-T4-T1d a2	CRISPR KO	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
StUBI::PPE-RYmax a1	CRISPR Prime editing	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
StUBI::GFP StUBI::PPE-RYmax o2	CRISPR Prime editing	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Spectinomycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
StUBI::GFP StUBI::zCas9i o2	CRISPR KO	Dicots	Binary	Golden Gate	Spectinomycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
StUBI::GFP StUBI::PPE-RYmax T1-T1d-T3-T4-T10-T11 a2	CRISPR Prime editing	Plants	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	Fluorescence	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
pUPD2-StUBI10	Promoter	Plants	High copy	Golden Gate	Chloramphenicol	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
pTwist-M1 Alt	gRNA scaffold	Plants	High copy	GW Entry	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
pTwist-M1 Plx	gRNA scaffold	Plants	High copy	GW Entry	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
StU6::pegT1 a1	pegRNA scaffold	Plants	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
StU6::pegT2 a2	pegRNA scaffold	Plants	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
StU6::pegT3 a1	pegRNA scaffold	Plants	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
StU6::pegT4 a2	pegRNA scaffold	Plants	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
StU6::pegT5 a2	pegRNA scaffold	Plants	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
StU6::pegT1d a2	pegRNA scaffold	Plants	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
StU6::pegT8 a1	pegRNA scaffold	Plants	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
StU6::pegT9 a2	pegRNA scaffold	Plants	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
o1 T1-T2	pegRNA scaffold	Plants	Binary	Golden Gate	Spectinomycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
o2 T3-T4	pegRNA scaffold	Plants	Binary	Golden Gate	Spectinomycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
a1 T1-T2-T3-T4	pegRNA scaffold	Plants	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
o1 T1-T2-T3-T4-T1d	pegRNA scaffold	Plants	Binary	Golden Gate	Spectinomycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
o1 T1-T2-T3-T4-T15	pegRNA scaffold	Plants	Binary	Golden Gate	Spectinomycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel

StU6::pegT10 a1	pegRNA scaffold	Plants	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
StU6::pegT11 a2	pegRNA scaffold	Plants	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
o2 T10-T11	pegRNA scaffold	Plants	Binary	Golden Gate	Spectinomycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
a2 T10-T11	pegRNA scaffold	Plants	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
o1 T1-T1d	pegRNA scaffold	Plants	Binary	Golden Gate	Spectinomycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
a1 T1-T1d-T3-T4	pegRNA scaffold	Plants	Binary	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
o1 T1-T1d-T3-T4-T10-T11	pegRNA scaffold	Plants	Binary	Golden Gate	Spectinomycin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
pEn Sa Chimera ALt	gRNA scaffold	Plants	High copy	GW Entry	Ampicillin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
pEn Sa Chimera Plx	gRNA scaffold	Plants	High copy	GW Entry	Ampicillin	None	DH10B	INRAE-Ploudaniel
pML-SpCas9	CRISPR KO	Plants	High copy	Golden Gate	Spectinomycin	None	DH5a	ILVO
pML-LbCpf1-GFP	CRISPR KO	Plants	High copy	Golden Gate	Spectinomycin	Fluorescence	DH5a	ILVO
pML-LbCpf1	CRISPR KO	Plants	High copy	Golden Gate	Spectinomycin	None	DH5a	ILVO
pML-SaCas9	CRISPR KO	Plants	High copy	Golden Gate	Spectinomycin	None	DH5a	ILVO
pAS_CD-entry_LbCpf1	CRISPR KO	Plants	High copy	Golden Gate	Ampicillin	None	DH5a	ILVO
pML_FG-entry_Prom-Scaf for LbCpf1	CRISPR KO	Plants	High copy	Golden Gate	Ampicillin	None	DH5a	ILVO
pML_FG-entry_Prom-Scaf for LbCpf1_AarI-RS	CRISPR KO	Plants	High copy	Golden Gate	Ampicillin	None	DH5a	ILVO
pAS_CD-entry_SaCas9	CRISPR KO	Plants	High copy	Golden Gate	Ampicillin	None	DH5a	ILVO
pML_FG-entry_Prom-Scaf for SaCas9_AarI-RS	CRISPR KO	Plants	High copy	Golden Gate	Ampicillin	None	DH5a	ILVO
pCDB-Cas9-ccdB	CRISPR KO	Plants	High copy	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	None	DH5a	ILVO
pGGA-AtU6-ccdB-B	Promoter (PolIII)	Plants	High copy	Golden Gate	Ampicillin	None	DH5a	ILVO
pK_TadAMax10-Cas9D10-GFP	CRISPR Nickase	Plants	High copy	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	Fluorescence	DH5a	ILVO
pK_APOBEC3-Cas9D10-GFP	CRISPR Nickase	Plants	High copy	Golden Gate	Kanamycin	Fluorescence	DH5a	ILVO

Annex 2: MTA to be signed when ordering plasmids from VectorVault

Material Transfer Agreement

By placing an order for one or more vectors, you agree to receive and use such vectors strictly in accordance with the terms and conditions as detailed in this material transfer agreement.

- ***All vectors ordered are to be used strictly for non-commercial academic research purposes only.***
- ***We ask you to provide appropriate acknowledgment of the source of the vectors by referring to the original scientific publications describing the vectors. Specific other requirements may be applicable for certain vectors.***

Whereas VIB has developed a collection of destination, expression and entry vectors, listed on the website <https://vectorvault.vib.be> compatible with various types of cloning protocols,

Whereas in developing the binary destination and expression vectors, VIB used the nptII, Hyg and Bar selectable markers isolated from the pGreen vector that was obtained from John Innes Centre (hereinafter “JIC Material”),

Whereas reference to JIC Material in the articles below only applies in the event Material is a T-DNA binary destination or a T-DNA binary expression vector,

Whereas Recipient wants to obtain certain vectors described in the order form, which together with any parts or sub-units, descendants, progeny, mutants, mutations or other derivatives thereof are referred to as the ‘Material’ for use in the research project described in the order form (hereinafter “Research”),

Whereas VIB is prepared to supply Recipient with Material under the terms and conditions as set forth hereinafter,

Whereas for certain Material (i.e. pHUGE_Redseed, pHUGE_Red, pK7WG-TRAP, pK7WG-INTACT-AT, pK7WG-INTACT-SI, pMG304, pMG305, pMG306, pMG413, pMG414, pMG415, pMG416, pMG423, pMG424, pMG425, pMG426) specific terms and conditions apply as detailed in article 9, VIB and Recipient agree as follows:

1. VIB shall supply the Material to Recipient as soon as possible after the conclusion of this material transfer agreement. VIB shall remain the sole owner of the Material.
2. Recipient shall utilize the Material only for research purposes and more specifically shall only use the Material to conduct the Research. Recipient shall not use the Material or any material containing Material in field trials. Nothing in this Material Transfer Agreement shall be deemed to grant Recipient any rights under any patent or patent application, nor any rights to use the Material for any product or process for commercial purposes.
3. Recipient shall not transmit by any means whatsoever all or part of the Material to any third party without the prior or written consent of VIB.
4. VIB does not warrant that the use of the Material does not or will not infringe any patent. VIB is under no obligation to obtain or provide licenses that may be required for the use of the Material by

the Recipient. In particular, VIB does not warrant that the use of the JIC Material does not or will not infringe any patent. Furthermore, neither VIB nor John Innes Centre is under any obligation to obtain or provide licenses that may be required for the use of the JIC Material by the Recipient.

5. Recipient agrees to provide appropriate acknowledgement of the source of the Material in all publications and presentations based on the use of the Material by referring to the original scientific articles indicated in <https://vectorvault.vib.be> for each vector.
6. Recipient will use the Material in compliance with all laws and regulations both nationally and internationally, including regulations for work with recombinant material. The Material is experimental in nature, and is provided by VIB with no warranties, express or implied, including any warranty of merchantability, title or fitness for a particular use. In no event shall VIB (nor John Innes Centre) be liable to Recipient against any loss, claim or demand made by Recipient, or against Recipient by any other party, due to or arising from Recipient's use of the Material and/or Developments except when caused by the gross negligence or willful misconduct of VIB or John Innes Centre.
7. This Material Transfer Agreement will be governed and interpreted in accordance with the Belgian law. If Recipient is a US university or institution, parties agree to remain silent on law.
8. Additional terms and conditions are valid for the specific vectors:

8.1. Vectors **pHUGE_RedSeed and PHUGE_Red**

Recipient acknowledges that vectors pHUGE_RedSeed and PHUGE_Red were obtained from Wageningen University (WUR) and contain parts of pMF1 which is proprietary to Foundation Stichting Dienst Landbouwkundig Onderzoek (DLO), and that pYL7AC7, from which pHUGE_RedSeed and PHUGE_Red are constructed, for academic purpose, is permitted free of charge by the Oji Paper Co., Ltd (OJI), who is intellectual property right holder of pYL7AC7.\

8.1.1. For Vectors pHUGE_RedSeed and PHUGE_Red article 1 of the above agreement shall be replaced by 'VIB shall supply the Material to Recipient as soon as possible after the conclusion of this material transfer agreement. VIB shall remain the sole owner of the Material. pHUGE_RedSeed and PHUGE_Red are owned by Plant Research International and the Laboratory of Molecular Biology of Wageningen University and should be respected as such.'

8.1.2. For the sake of clarity, Recipient shall not modify pHUGE_RedSeed and PHUGE_Red.'

8.1.3. For Vectors pHUGE_RedSeed and PHUGE_Red article 4 of the above agreement shall be replaced by 'VIB does not warrant that the use of the Material does not or will not infringe any patent. Neither VIB nor WUR nor DLO nor Oji is under any obligation to obtain or provide licenses that may be required for the use of the Material by the Recipient. In particular, VIB does not warrant that the use of the Material does not or will not infringe any patent. Furthermore, neither VIB nor John Innes Centre is under any obligation to obtain or provide licenses that may be required for the use of the JIC Material by the Recipient.'

8.1.4. For Vectors pHUGE_RedSeed and PHUGE_Red article 5 of the above agreement shall be replaced by 'Recipient agrees to provide appropriate acknowledgement of the source of the Material in all publications and presentations based on the use of the Material by referring to the original scientific articles

indicated in the (<https://vectorvault.vib.be>) for each vector. A copy of all publications presenting results obtained using pHUGE_RedSeed and PHUGE_Red is to be sent to Plant Research International and the Laboratory of Molecular Biology of Wageningen University immediately upon publication. A copy of all publications presenting results obtained using pHUGE_RedSeed or PHUGE_Red is to be sent to Dr Masatomo Kobayashi (kobayai@rtc.riken.jp).

8.1.5. For Vectors pHUGE_RedSeed and PHUGE_Red article 6 of the above agreement shall be replaced by ‘Recipient will use the Material in compliance with all laws and regulations both nationally and internationally, including regulations for work with recombinant material. The material is experimental in nature, and is provided by VIB with no warranties, express or implied, including any warranty of merchantability, title, or fitness for a particular use. Recipient will indemnify VIB, OJI, WUR and DLO and will hold VIB, OJI, WUR and DLO harmless from any claims or liabilities which might arise as a result of Recipient’s use of the Material. In particular, Recipient will hold harmless John Innes Centre and its governors, officers, employees and agents from any and all liabilities or claims brought by third parties resulting from the transfer to and use of the JIC Material by the Recipient.’

8.2.Vectors **PK7WG-TRAP, PK7WG-INTACT-AT and PK7WG-INTACT-SI**

Recipient acknowledges that Vectors PK7WG-TRAP, PK7WG-INTACT-AT and PK7WG-INTACT-SI are jointly owned by VIB and UC Davis. VIB has the right to distribute the material.

8.2.1. For Vectors PK7WG-TRAP, PK7WG-INTACT-AT and PK7WG-INTACT-SI article 1 of the above agreement shall be replaced by ‘VIB shall supply the Material to Recipient as soon as possible after the conclusion of this material transfer agreement. VIB and UC Davis shall remain the owners of the Material.’

8.2.2. For Vectors PK7WG-TRAP, PK7WG-INTACT-AT and PK7WG-INTACT-SI article 5 of the above agreement shall be replaced by ‘Recipient agrees to provide appropriate acknowledgement of the source of the Material in all publications and presentations based on the use of the Material referring to the original scientific articles indicated in (<https://vectorvault.vib.be>) for each vector. In particular, Recipient shall acknowledge Dr Siobhan Brady and UC Davis as source of the material.

8.3.Vectors **pMG304, pMG305, pMG306, pMG413, pMG414, pMG415, pMG416, pMG423, pMG424, pMG425, pMG426**

These vectors can only be ordered if Recipient is either a university or other institution of higher education, a government agency, or a nonprofit organization.

8.3.1. For Vectors pMG304, pMG305, pMG306, pMG413, pMG414, pMG415, pMG416, pMG423, pMG424, pMG425, pMG426 article 2 of the above agreement shall be replaced by ‘Recipient shall utilize the Material only for research purposes and more specifically shall only use the Material to conduct the Research. Recipient shall not use the Material or any material containing Material for commercial purposes, including using the Material to perform contract research, to screen compound libraries, to produce or manufacture products for general sale, or to conduct research activities that result in any sale, lease, license or transfer of the Material to a for-profit organization. Nothing in this Material Transfer Agreement shall be deemed to grant Recipient any rights under any patent or patent application, nor any rights to use the Material for any product or process for commercial purposes.

Please tick this box to confirm agreement with the terms and conditions detailed in the agreement above

